

THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY IS ON THE VERGE OF A NEW ERA OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS

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Annotation. This article covers the automotive industry's new era of technological progress and the DM-I super hybrid models and electric cars of BYD.

Keywords: car, hybrid model, electric car, technology, development, industry.

UzAuto is on the verge of a new era that will allow you to go ahead at least 10 years in the production of modern cars, thinking about the future generation.

In Tashkent, the presentation of the DM-I super hybrid models and electric cars of BYD, one of the leaders of the world car market, took place. For example, every tenth light car sold in the world in 2022 is an electric car. They are a significant aspect—they are produced only in advanced countries. The fact that the automobile industry of Uzbekistan is on the eve of a new era of technological development now sets the stage for the best-selling NEV cars to take over from the Uzbek market.

At a time when the whole world is looking for innovative solutions, Uzbekistan is confidently following the path of joining a number of countries that have mastered advanced technologies. Thinking about the future generation, Uzbekistan is on the verge of a new era, which will allow at least 10 years to advance in the production of energy, modern cars. This is another proof that Uzbekistan has every opportunity to become the first in the CIS and 14 countries in the world. Today, the fact that the Uzbek automobile industry is moving towards its position in the international arena is a sign that there are still great heights ahead. The development of scientific potential of Engineers of Uzbekistan, as well as further development of techniques related to the field, is taking place today.

Cars operating on the basis of new energy sources in Uzbekistan are not only an economical and environmentally friendly means of transportation, it is:

1. Leading countries with high engineering potential are technologies that offer the opportunity to penetrate, create opportunities in science and production, and expand, in general, to take a step forward in all areas.
2. The development of new high technologies that have not been used before in Uzbekistan. This is the creation of million-Dollar products from cheap raw materials, hususan, batteries, electrodvigatels, electronic blocks, microchips, as well as material processing, Organization of raw material processing.
3. In Uzbekistan, engineering, product design, adaptation of cars to climate and road conditions, creation of test laboratories, study and introduction of modern standards, integration of electroenergetics — industry and science is to increase the capacity of Science and specialists in such science-based areas.
4. The development of software for smart cars and robotic production equipment, as well as capable of analyzing large volumes of data and creating centralized data centers — is the maturation of a new generation of specialists of a high category in the IT field.

5. Is the organization of the production of high-tech products using science-based technologies. The introduction of the world's advanced experience into the practice of Uzbekistan will create the necessary conditions for the country that will provide incentives for the acquisition of new knowledge and the development of Science in such directions as intelligent sensors, artificial intelligence, new generation information technologies (IoT), industrial design, engineering design.

6. In the era of fuel shortages and environmental problems, energy resource savings are the next step — the developed infrastructure for electric vehicle power stations will lead to a reduction in transportation costs.

The transition to the production of a new type of transport means a look into the future. In the future, in an economically developed, intellectual potential and competitive state, it is necessary not only to increase the number of citizens who have the means of transportation, but also to continue the efforts towards the formation of many as yet abstract and undiscovered innovators, creators and scientists.

Innovation in the automotive industry along with capacity assessment, many factors are identified that influence competitiveness from within creation, production of innovations of various levels in order to increase allocate factors that contribute to the organization of the possibility of application in the processes. Modern conditions for the development of the national economy are noticeable use of the innovation potential of economic entities at the level this continuously changing external environment, determined by position, level and hand provides the necessary level of competitiveness in conditions and promotes activity keeps. In doing so, focus on 2 important aspects of innovation capacity assessment we found it worthwhile to focus. These are:

- first of all, in the assessment, first of all, each of the innovative potentials a systematic review of the component was required, not separately. Only automobile industry enterprises as a result of their interaction in a single system the structural components of the innovation capacity allow to achieve high efficiency gives. These are the results obtained from the activities of individual organizers is much more than the arithmetic sum;
- secondly, innovation capacity is not only the volume of accumulated resources perhaps, their quality, composition, balance of the organizers it is also characterized by degree and efficiency of use. Resources improving the quality content of the existing innovation capacity their quantity provides growth without increase.

Innovation capacity building strategy first development, introduction, use and implementation of innovations to the general potential of automotive enterprises by assessing the result serves.

References:

1. Йўлдошев Н.Қ., Мирсаидова Ш.А., Голдман Й.Д. Инновацион менеджмент – Т.; ТДИУ, дарслик, 2011. 6-б.
2. Қодиров Т.У. “Автомобиль транспорти рақобатдошлиги: ташкилийиқтисодий механизмлар” Иқтисодиёт фанлари доктори илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган монографияси.-Т.: Тошкент автомобиль йўллари институти, 2014. – Б. 241.

3. “Автомобиль саноати корхоналарининг инновацион салоҳиятини ошириш ва уни бошқариш” Мамаджонов Дилшод Гафурович. “Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар” илмий электрон журнали. № 2, март-апрель, 2018 йил.
4. <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2023/03/17/uzauto/>.“Avtomobilsozlik sanoati yangi texnologik taraqqiyot davri ostonasida”.

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